

An Economic Study of Health Status in Rural Child with Special Reference in Meelaneelitha Nallur Block

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Introduction

"Your genes are the building blocks, yours nutrition is the mother & your environment is the architect that shape your destiny"

- KE Elizabeth

The constitutional provision of a right for optimum survival, many children are not getting the benefit of services like primary health care, adequate nutrition, proper environment, stimulation, education, recreation and tender loving parental care. Even though the precise mechanism is not clear, it has been established that growth, development and intelligence of such children are at risk. Structural and biochemical changes have been demonstrated in the growing brain due to malnutrition.

However, the existing child welfare programmes are not sufficient to meet all the needs and demands. Scientific ideas are transforming from generation to generation and igniting a thought that brain of the 2 year old children grows much faster than in all other ages. Primary health care and nutritional supplementation have failed to deliver the desired outcome. The stimulation along with nutritional supplementation may be a better choice. Health care thus is the Prime area of development that should be focused more in any country.

Health Status of Rural Child Development

Growth and development are sometimes used interchangeably. But growth implies an increase the size of organs and body and development mean differentiation and malnutrition of function.

Factors affecting child development

Development of the child is determined by the following factors

Genetic factor

Genetic factors are not only final limits of biological potential, but also they are intimately interwoven with the environment.

Physical Factor

The growth of a child is affected by both prenatal and postnatal physical insults.

Nutritional Factors

Nutrition factors like chronic malnutrition affect the physical growth..

Emotional Factors

Position of the child in the family and the child rearing practices in the family and community that affect the growth and development of the children comes under the emotional factors.

Social Cultural Factor

The behaviour of children can be limited or expanded through the socio-cultural factors. Common activities like sitting and walking will be influenced by the conventional expectations. It also reflects in the nutritional status of the child.

In the developing nations, the health and nutritional status of the children are indicated by their height and weight. Maternal education is mandatory for child health. In the countries like peru, there is still no maternal education in the rural areas.

Statement of the Problem

Health is a vital aspect of the survival of the human. The concepts, knowledge, skills and infrastructure for healthcare has been evolved through the evolution of human civilisation in various societies. However, due to gender bias, the health priorities for men and women have been different in traditions and affection. Health is wealth” is an adage. More importance was given to health even from the time immemorial, and so people taking all efforts to attain. To economists, health is a crucial factor for economic development, and to sociologist it is vital for social development. It is very significant for medical people to control both communicable and non-communicable diseases.

Objectives of the Study

- To identify the health problem of children in Meelaneelithanallur block due to malnutrition
- To suggest a few recommendations to improve the health status of the children in Meelaneelithanallur block.

Review of Literature

In India, there were distance sages of rising and fall in the status of children. Large volumes of literature have been developed on the malnutrition of children. Some of the literature relevant to this study was reviewed in this section.

DIPA SINHA (2015) Says that the data from the rapid survey on children conducted in 201-14 released after an inexplicable delay and still in a summary fashion, show some but patchy progress between 2005-06 and 201-14 in maternal and child health indicators. While economic growth rates accelerated after 2005-06, this period also saw several of interventions by the central government in about health and nutrition, including the introduction of the national rural health mission (NRHM), Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY) and the expansion of the integrated child development services (ICDS). That the increase in the coverage of antenatal care (ANS) services has not been as much as that in delivery services, the percentage of women making ANC visits three or more time (as recommended) has gone up from 52% to only 63% and a similar allotment of women has reported having an ANC in the first trimester according to the RSOC data, of the mother who were aware of the JSY and Janani Shishu Suraksha Karyakram (JSSK) schemes, 47% availed of the JSY but

only 14% availed of any benefits of the JSSK.. While the JSY provides for a cash incentive for institutional delivery, the JSSK provides for cashless treatment for all services related to maternal and neonatal health.

Methodology

This study is used Primary data and as well as secondary data. Primary data is collect from the sample respondents through well-structured interview schedule and Questionnaire. Government Gazettes, internet etc. Sample- Nurse, Doctors, Anganwadi teachers, Anganwadi abayas midwife form PHC, were collected through personal visit to the home. A Preliminary interview schedule were constructed and administered to 300 households. House wives were also interviewed for more information. In addition to this, the informal discussion was also held with heads of the families or other members of the families to cross -check the information. I have used the frequency test for verifying the primary data with the use of Diets sheet. The present study have been undertaken about health expenditure in Meelaneelithanallur block in Tirunelveli District. From the total population of 95104, the researcher has selected 300 respondents, a sample by using simple random sampling method. Sample- Nurse - 100, Anganwadi teachers - 100, Midwife from PHC-- 100,

‘Diets Sheet ‘Per Day’

Diet requires to be modified by dietitians to suit the needs of individual patients in different parts of the world. Nutrition professionals like to toss around terms like “diet” “Nutrition” “low-fat” and the like when people say they “on a diet”. It sounds like they are restricting something or eliminating certain ingredients. In reality, a diet is a normal pittern of eating. One could be on the pizza and beer diet, or the eating lots of fruit and vegetable diet. A diet is what one typically eats. Nutrients are lost by either being discarded or chemically changed. Nutrients differ in their susceptibility to misfortune, depending on their chemical and their location within a food. Using food preparation methods maximising nutrient retention is most important when the die contains few good sources of nutrients. Occasional use of ways that cause considerable nutrient loss is not a cause for alarm. However, if a few nutritious foods are eaten, conserving the value of food pins importance. Fortunately, methods that help retain the nutritive value of foods are methods that result in tasty, attractive food—food that entices the eater to enjoy a nutritious meal. The following suggested methods reduce the loss of flavour and colour, as well as the loss of nutrients. They are also economical. Many of them save time. The following table analysis the situations of the respondents in terms of diets sheet per day

Table 1.1

Diet Sheet Per Day	Frequency	Percent
Vegetables	207	8.9
Eggs	378	16.3
Fruits	184	7.9
Dosa	205	8.9
Cereals	114	4.9
Milk	340	14.7
wheat product	263	11.4
Idli	268	11.6
Rice	355	15.3
Total	2314	100

Source: computed from primary data

It is observe from table 4.4 that out of the 400 respondents, 207 took vegetables daily, and it comes to 8.9%. 378 consume Eggs daily, and it is 16.3%.184 ate Fruits daily, and it comes to 7.9%. 205 consume Dosa daily, and it is 7.9%. 114 took cereals daily and it comes to 4.9%. 340 took Milk daily, and it is 14.7%.263ate wheat product daily, and it comes to 11.4%. 268 takes Idli daily, and it comes to 11.6%.355 ate Rice per day, and it is 15.3%.

Figure 1.1 Diet Sheet Per Day of the Respondents

Findings

A researcher has made some observations and derived some conclusions while carrying out the research work.

- The study also makes it clear that out of 2314 respondents, 16.35% are Diets sheet with Egg to consume daily. Whereas the remaining minimum 4.9% are Diets sheet per day cereals. Thus, it enlightens the truth that a majority of the respondents consume Egg per day.

Suggestions

Following suggestions are given to improve the health of children,

- The government is awareness camps to the parents regarding child health, mentality, and various mind related issues should be regularly conducte through Anganwadi. This better opportunity for the child and her mother.
- The government should increase the number of doctors and nurses in the primary health centres, and the government should make necessary arrangement to open HSCS within Meelaneelithanallur Block. Besides government should earmark more funds for the procurement of drugs and medicines, which may be supplied free of cost for the needy.

Conclusion

The present study helped to focus on the major sickness among the children, the main reason for the malnutrition, water porn diseases for children, the economic atmosphere of parents of malnutrition children etc and helped to know the fact that the care from parents to their children trouble much, they should care their children with enough knowledge about their health condition there is a big role for the government to spend enough find in order to build a strong, healthy and empowered future India.

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